

Teaching English as a second language for non native speakers

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Abstract: *All living things have some means of communicating information to others in their group, which is ultimately essential to their survival. Some use vocal noises, others use physical movements or facial expressions. Many people use different methods.*

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English teaching methodology, because the builders of the Tower of Babel spoke different languages, the society needed translators. Translators were appreciated everywhere. Until recently, a foreign language was more of a hobby than a harsh reality. Knowing a foreign language means being an esthete, belonging to a certain circle, or (the most harmless option) - being called an eccentric. But times are changing. Any house you know starts with an architectural plan. Now we are more and more afraid of the huge fortress called "Foreign language", on top of which the flag (mostly British) flies proudly. And in this case, knowledge of modern teaching methods serves as a necessary plan.¹

Teaching English as a second language is an outdated term because students can

¹ „What's the difference between TEFL, TESL, TESOL and CELTA?“ (en). Teach Away (25-avgust 2021-yil).

speak multiple languages before learning English. Students who learn English in their home country, usually at school, are EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students. In general, English Language Learners are called ELLs (English Language Learners).

Teaching English as a Second Language (TESL) refers to teaching English to students whose first language is not English (that is, English is not considered their first language). The teaching profession has historically used different names for TEFL and TESL; however, the general term Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages (TESOL) is increasingly used to describe the profession. TESOL as a broad term encompasses both TESL and TEFL. Both native English speakers and non-native speakers are successfully trained to become English teachers. When teaching English to English as a Second Language Learners or ELLs, it is recommended, but not always required, to take written and oral tests to determine English proficiency.²

Communicative language teaching (CLT) is important both as a means and as an end goal of language learning. Despite a number of criticisms, communicative language teaching continues to be popular, particularly in Japan, Taiwan, and Europe. CBSE (Central Board of Secondary Education) in India has also adopted this approach in its branches.

In recent years, the task-based approach to language learning in CLT has become widespread. Proponents believe that CLT is important in developing and improving speaking, writing, listening, and reading skills, and it prevents students

² „Abbreviations and Acronyms in the Field of English Education“. Globally Taught. Globally Taught (13-iyul 2021-yil).

from just passively listening to the teacher without interacting. Dogme is a similar communicative approach that encourages teaching without published textbooks while emphasizing a conversational relationship between students and teacher.

Blended learning is a combination of multimedia elements (also known as computer-assisted language learning) in a virtual learning environment (VLE) with classroom instruction, teacher and peer support. Using blended learning technology, it can provide students with a large amount of understandable information through video and other types of multimedia, even without the presence of a teacher.³

Advances in technology have also made it possible to take TEFL qualifications online. Students can enroll in online courses accredited by organizations such as the British Council or Cambridge ESOL. There is no single general accrediting body for TEFL; however, private for-profit companies are also known today to create accreditation affiliates and use them to defraud customers.

Study materials are divided into modules where students are tested. Support, i.e. helping students, is provided by tutors and tutors can be contacted by email. Upon successful completion of the last module, the student is awarded a certificate that comes digitally or can be mailed to the student's address. Obtaining such a certification can be beneficial, as many employers require TEFL certification.

Qualification requirements vary considerably from one country to another and between employers within a country. Many institutions also offer teaching without a degree or teaching certificate. Some institutions consider it necessary to be a native speaker at the MA TESOL level. Additionally, a university degree in

³ Divine. „The Fundamentals of Teaching English as a Foreign Language, 6th edition“. ITA Press.

English Language and Literature can be as valuable as any professional degree. Other institutions consider proof of English language proficiency, a university degree and basic teaching qualifications to be sufficient. However, the level of academic qualification is not solidified as the most important qualification, as many schools are more interested in a person's interpersonal skills. For those who want to enter the scientific field, some literature can be as important as the qualification, especially if the literature concerns the use of English in the field. Only in cases where the demand for teachers is high and there are no legal requirements, employers (including some countries) may hire candidates who do not meet certain requirements. Every country is different, and hiring depends on the demand for English teachers and the teacher's previous teaching and life experience. The TEFL industry and language schools have decided that a minimum of 100 hours of course completion is the standard for a recognized/accredited TEFL course.

Private language schools may require a certificate of successful completion of a course of at least 100 hours when hiring teachers. Major programs like EPIK offer higher salaries to teachers who complete any TEFL course online or otherwise (provided the program meets the minimum 100-hour requirement). [14] Internet-based TEFL courses are accepted worldwide, particularly in Asia, where China, Korea, Taiwan, and Japan have the largest job markets. The minimum TEFL requirement for China is 120 hours.

In Asia, there is a tendency to hire TEFL teachers based on superficial criteria such as race (Caucasians are preferred) and an English teacher or native English speaker is "white". 'should be', this is particularly evident in Thailand, where it is a

major employer of TEFL teachers and where advertisements are often open to native English speakers. This is partly due to commercial expectations in the private sector, where parents believe that additional fees for TEFL teachers should be guaranteed by an American or British TEFL teacher, while schools risk losing students to do so. does not come.

In some cases, age or gender requirements may also apply. In some countries outside of Europe and the Americas, such as the Middle East, schools may hire men over women or vice versa, and they may only hire teachers within a certain age range, usually between 20 and 40 years old. In China, however, age requirements may vary across the country according to provincial government regulations. Anyone under the age of 19 can teach TEFL, but usually only on a voluntary basis, such as in a refugee camp.⁴

As in most fields, salary depends largely on education, training, seniority, and experience. As with most foreign labor, employment conditions vary depending on the level of economic development and how many people want to live there. In relatively poor countries, even low wages can equate to a comfortable middle-class lifestyle. EFL teachers who want to earn money often aim to work in high-demand countries in East Asia, such as China, South Korea and Japan. The Middle East is also often cited as one of the best paying regions, although a better qualification is usually required, i.e. at least a CELTA and a couple of years' experience.⁵

In the United Arab Emirates (UAE), salaries vary depending on the school you work at (International School or Public School) and are calculated including

⁴ „What is TEFL?“. International TEFL Academy (2021).

⁵ REF. „Do ESL Teachers Need an English Proficiency Test?“ (en-US). Rapid English Fluency (14-sentyabr 2020-yil).

wages, as well as other benefits such as housing, flights and insurance.

There is a risk of exploitation by employers. Spain has backed the criticism, given the large number of small and medium-sized businesses (including TEFL schools) that regularly forgo teachers' social insurance combinations as a means of increasing profits. As a result, most teachers are entitled to less unemployment or sick pay than they would be entitled to if wages and contributions were published in accordance with the law. Similar situations are more common in countries with labor laws that may not apply or be enforced against foreign workers. The employer can ignore the provisions of the contract, especially some provisions regarding working hours, working days and termination payments.

Language, cultural or simply time constraints for foreign teachers can make it difficult in some cases to demand the wages and conditions stipulated in their contracts. Therefore, some conflicts arise from cross-cultural misunderstandings. Many teachers who are unable to adjust to living and working abroad may decide to quit after a few months. It can also be difficult for teachers to recognize which jobs are legitimate, as many leading recruitment agencies allow unfiltered paid postings. Therefore, teachers can turn to the help of recruitment agencies that work only with reputable schools.⁶

Classical approach to learning a foreign language In this regard, the classical approach to learning a foreign language has also changed somewhat, but the incomparable principles of the "classics" of Russian language methods have been preserved. Sometimes they are actively used in schools of other methodological directions. The classical course is designed for students of different ages and often

⁶ Van Hattum, Ton. „Communicative Approach Rethought“. tonvanhattum.com.br (2006).

involves learning the language "from scratch". The teacher's tasks include the traditional but important aspects of forming the grammatical base of pronunciation, eliminating psychological and linguistic barriers that interfere with communication. "Classic" has not changed its goals, but the methods are already different due to the new approach.

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